

Cross-Cultural Analysis of Sufi Elements in Rumi and Kabir's Poetry

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Abstract— This paper conducts a comparative analysis of the poetry of two prominent Sufi poets, Rumi and Kabir, focusing on their shared themes and cultural influences. Through examination of primary sources- "The Essential Rumi" and "One Hundred Poems of Kabir," alongside relevant secondary literature, recurring themes such as love, unity, and ego dissolution are explored. Employing a thematic coding process, common elements in their works are identified, offering insights into the spiritual depth of their poetry. The overarching objective of this research is to contribute to literary and religious studies by revealing the expression of the Sufi tradition in the accessible language of Rumi and Kabir.

Keywords— Sufi poetry, Rumi, Kabir, Comparative analysis, Spiritual themes

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Historical Evolution of Sufism

The history of Sufism spans from the early days of Islam till date. Sufi traditions can be traced back to the meditative practices of Prophet Muhammad in Mecca and his teachings like vocal praying. There are also references in Quran about it which lay the groundwork for later practices in Sufism. However, the term Sufi came much later in around 7th or 8th century in a time of political turmoil. This was a time of rationalism where importance of love and spiritual experiences was emphasized by the Sufis to create a balance in the Islamic society. From 10th to 12th centuries, with Sufi scholars working towards the systemization of terminology and practices, Sufism started gaining popularity and acceptance resulting in the formation of new Sufi orders. By the 13th century, Sufism emerged as a proper discipline.

Rumi in Anatolia

Rumi was born in Balkh (now Afghanistan) in 1207. He moved to Anatolia (modern-day Turkey) later on with his family. There, he settled in the city of Konya which was under the rule of Seljuk Empire at that time. His worldview and poetry were influenced by various cultures in the region like Turkish, Persian and Arabic. The Mevlevi Order was established by his followers after his death because his spiritual teachings on themes like love and union deeply affected the people there. His insights combined with the cultural traditions to create a Sufi group Whirling Dervishes.

Kabir in 15th-century India

Kabir lived in 15th century India. He was a mystical poet who's work got deeply influenced by the socio-political situation of that time, particularly and majorly the Bhakti movement. The movement emphasized on principles like devotion and direct experience of the divine rather than through the traditional ritualistic methodologies. Kabir blended Islam and Hinduism in his work and that is what makes him unique. Themes like love, union and search for the truth are seen in his poetry or dohe. He was a figure representing inclusivity in 15th century India.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The influence of Rumi and Kabir on mystic poetry individually has been widely researched upon. However, there isn't much available about the comparison between the poetry by them. Specifically, no works regarding the cultural contexts that shaped their works. Therefore, the aim of this research paper is to fill the gap in scholarly studies by the performing a cross-cultural analysis of Sufi elements in their poetry.

1.3 Research Objectives

The aim is to study the Sufi elements in the poetry of Rumi and Kabir for a cross-cultural analysis comparing the two. The goal is to highlight the common themes, symbols and philosophies in their works.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The research aims to provide a better understanding of the Sufi aspect in Rumi and Kabir poetry and the influence of culture and religion on it. Hence, it attempts to contribute in the fields of literature, cultural studies and religious studies.

1.5 Research Questions

The research question focuses on how Sufi elements in the poetry of Rumi and Kabir are influenced by the cultural, religious, and spiritual context of their time and how Sufi themes and symbols are used to convey the same.

1.6 Scope and Limitations

The focus of the research is on the key writings of Rumi and Kabir to study the Sufi themes. The potential limitations are related to time, translation, resources and subjectivity in interpretation.

1.7 Definition of Key Terms

Sufism

Sufism is the mystical aspect of Islam which emphasizes direct and experiential pursuit of the divine. Rituals like dhikr or the remembrance of God, pursuit of God through love, dissolution of the ego and meditative practices are some of the core principles Sufis believe in.

Cross-Cultural Analysis

Cross-cultural analysis is the comparative study of cultures across different societies. Here, Sufi elements in the poetry of Rumi and Kabir are cross-culturally analysed across the Anatolian and medieval Indian societies.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Sufism Overview

Synopsis of Sufism

Sufism is mostly considered as the mystical branch of Islam. It has a lot of rituals, concepts and philosophical perspectives. Sufis- the followers of Sufism practice to attain a direct and intimate relationship with God. The Quran and the Hadith, which are the sayings and deeds of the Prophet Muhammad did help with the framework for Sufi teachings. Spiritual growth along with inner purity are the core achievements of Sufism. Dhikr is the repeated recitation of the name of God or the holy and spiritual words which is one of the main ritualistic practices in it. It is through this practice that Sufi's develop a conscious awareness of the divine. Love in Sufi philosophy is the primary motivation behind the pursuit of the beloved by the lover. So, the idea of divine love is emphasised strongly in the Sufi philosophy. It is often portrayed in the works of both the poets. Rumi and Kabir present it in the same way as a path to connect to the divine instead of fear being the driving force behind it. It is termed as Ishq and it goes beyond the ideas of worldly or purely romantic passion. It is spiritual love. Annihilation of self or the destruction of ego is also one of the core principles in Sufism. Sufis believe that real spiritual progress can only come when the seeker's personal ego is defeated, and they are able to become one with the divine. Inner contemplation techniques like as meditation serve to rise above the confines of the ego and realize the reality of divine oneness. The main object of Sufi practice is meditation as a means of achieving mental clarity, soul cleansing, and developing an affinity with the infinite. Sufis attempt to attain a higher state of awareness and inner peace through a variety of meditation techniques in order to establish a simple means of communication with their beloved. Thus, Sufism is a spiritual path that emphasizes the pursuit of love, ego dissolution inner knowledge, and divine love as well as a spiritual bond with God through dhikr.

2.2 Comparative Studies in Sufi Poetry

Comparative studies on Sufi elements in poetry has been performed by some scholars in the field. Firstly, in *Mystical Dimensions of Islam* by Annemarie Schimmel, the focus is on language and culture shaping poetry across centuries and different languages. Another important work is *The Sufi Path of Love* by William Chittick which highlights the common themes among Persian mystics like Rumi and Attar. Here, the focus is on the language and historical context. Analysing these texts, it becomes clear that language, culture and historical context etc. does help to study the common Sufi themes in the poetry of various mystics. However, it fails to capture the subjective or personal mystical aspect of the experience of the poets. So, for this research, an attempt to combine it for an interdisciplinary approach has been made.

2.3 Rumi's Sufi Poetry

In this section some of the significant works that offer a critical appreciation of Rumi's life and work including teachings and poetry and the socio-cultural context of his time are discussed. Firstly, *The Essential Rumi* by Coleman Barks is an excellent resource to get a concise overview of Rumi's spiritual writings in English translation. Barks is a renowned translator and he presents a well curated collection of Rumi's poetry in this book. What makes this work stand out is Barks ability to preserve the essence of Rumi's original writings in the translated version. It becomes easier for English speakers to understand Rumi's ideas about love, enlightenment and spiritual truths through Barks work. So, *The Essential Rumi* provided readers with a contemporary stance on his ideas. "Rumi Past and Present, East and West" by Franklin D. Lewis is another useful resource for a more in-depth analysis of Rumi's life and the historical setting in which he lived. Lewis gives a comprehensive biography of Rumi, following his life as a scholar

beginning from his birthplace in Persia to his last residence. Considering the historical context in which Rumi's works were penned, an awareness of the details of his spiritual pursuit and the ongoing relevance of his teachings is gained. William C. Chittick's book "The Sufi Path of Love The Spiritual Teachings of Rumi" highlights the essence of Rumi's spirituality and the impact of love as the basis of Sufi mysticism. Chittick examines Rumi's theories regarding the need for the soul for union with the Beloved and divine love (Ishq). Chittick analyses Rumi's poetry and prose in order to present a critique of the Sufi approach to enlightenment. These texts are, all things considered, quite helpful in understanding Rumi's poetry and spiritual ideas. Barks' translations, Lewis's academic biography, and Chittick's insights into Sufi mysticism—all contribute to a better understanding of Rumi's lasting impact as one of the greatest spiritual poets in history—through their distinct points of view.

2.4 Kabir's Sufi Influence

To understand Kabir and the cultural influences that shaped his writings, it is important to look at various readings about his work, teachings and life. The *Bijak* of Kabir was written by Linda Hess and it serves as a foundational work that focuses on Kabir's collection of verses to understand his teachings. Hess talks about the *Bijak* and provides commentary and translations emphasizing on the meaning in a historical and cultural context. *Bijak's* writing provides a better understanding about Kabir's worldview including his criticism on religious orthodoxy and his appreciation of universal and spiritual love along with spiritual union and oneness. Chandan Sinha's "The Vision of Wisdom Kabir Selected Sakhis" offers an alternative viewpoint on Kabir's poetry. Sinha emphasizes a specific genre of his writings known as *sakhis* (couplets). Sinha, drawing on his expertise in Indian philosophy and literature, presents a collection of Kabir's *sakhis* along with commentary that explains their philosophical and spiritual themes. Through Sinha's analysis, one can explore Kabir's teachings on subjects such as reality, enlightenment, and ethical behavior in one's spiritual journey. Rabindranath Tagore's "One Hundred Poems of Kabir," translated by the Nobel laureate himself, provides a lyrical and poetic interpretation of Kabir's verses. Tagore, deeply influenced by Kabir's philosophy, infuses his poetic sensibilities into the translations, discussing Kabir's insights and philosophical profundity. Tagore's translations allow readers to experience the timelessness and universality of Kabir's poetry, transcending linguistic and cultural boundaries. Robert Bly's "Kabir Ecstatic Poems" offers a modern perspective on Kabir's verses, focusing on a selection of poems translated to highlight their ecstatic and mystical qualities. Bly, a celebrated poet and translator, imbues his unique poetic style into the translations, blending Kabir's verses with a sense of immediacy and emotional intensity. Through Bly's interpretations, a connection with the raw energy and spiritual passion of Kabir's poetry, and the transformative power of his words can be established. In addition to these literary works, other readings such as "Kabir in Indo-Muslim Visual and Literary Culture" by MK Mumtaz and "The Sant Movement and North Indian Sufis" by BB Lawrence also talk about Kabir's impact on the Indian subcontinent beyond poetry. These studies highlight Kabir's enduring legacy as a spiritual figure whose teachings transcended religious and cultural boundaries, inspiring generations of seekers across the Indian subcontinent and beyond that as well. Through a detailed and deep examination of these readings, a deeper understanding of Kabir's life, teachings, and the cultural forces that shaped his poetry can be attained.

Chapter 3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

A qualitative research design is adopted in order to analyse the poetry in depth. Primary sources are given a priority because the poems are to be analysed directly. "The Essential Rumi" by Coleman Barks and "One Hundred Poems of Kabir" translated by Rabindranath Tagore are chosen as the primary readings for this research.

3.2 Selection of Texts

These two collections are chosen for Rumi and Kabir's Sufi poetry because of the comprehensive and understandable overview of their works. Only two works are focused upon purposefully for a deeper analysis of the common Sufi themes.

3.3 Data Collection

Data collection involves the original poems by the poets and secondary readings by the scholars on the subject.

Primary Data Collection "The Essential Rumi" and "One Hundred Poems of Kabir" are the two books referred to for analysing the original poems.

Secondary Data Collection Research papers from scholars who have studied Rumi and Kabir's works are included for more information on the subject.

3.4 Data Analysis

Thematic Coding Process is used for data analysis involving the common themes in poems.

Thematic Coding Process This involves reading and marking the themes like love and union in the poems.

Comparative Framework This involves recognition of similarities and differences in the poems, considering language, culture, and historical context.

Chapter 4 Sufi Elements in Rumi's Verses

Rumi is one of the most important figures in Sufi tradition and poetry. His impact is felt till date centuries after his death and globally beyond time and space. His significance is also not confined to a nation or culture, it lives on in Persian, Urdu, Bengali, and Turkish literature. His influence extends across continents, inspiring poets like Ruckert, Goethe, Muhammad Iqbal, Rabindranath Tagore, Kazi Nazrul Islam, and Sattiyendra Nath Dutt. His contributions to Sufi poetry come from a deep sense of understanding of the mystical dimensions. His poetry revolves around various themes like love and search for the divine. One of his most famous works for its poetry quality is the Mathnavi which became a model for the aspiring Sufi poets. In today's world, where cultural understanding is of a great importance, his poetry connects people from different cultures and depicts Sufism as a gentle and tolerant side of Islam.

4.1 Mystical Imagery and Symbolism

Mystics often use imagery and symbols from day to day life experiences to express their spiritual experiences to the common masses. This tradition dates back to 9th century when early Sufi poets like Abu Yazid al-Bistami popularised symbols like wine, cup, and cupbearer. These symbols are still in used and can be commonly seen in the poetry of Ibn al-Farid, Iraqi and Yunus Emre and their followers.

In these verses

"Gone, inner and outer, no moon, no ground or sky."

Rumi talks about how everything seems to disappear – the moon, the ground, and the sky. It reflects the experience of going beyond the comprehensible or the ordinary which cannot be comprehended with usual understanding. This is a common experience amongst the Sufi mystics put in words by Rumi.

In these lines

"Don't hand me another glass of wine.
Pour it in my mouth.
I've lost the way to my mouth."

Here, Rumi uses the symbol of wine, a common metaphor in Sufi tradition for divine love. The absolute loss of self under intoxication and surrender to the divine or the cupbearer is depicted in these lines.

"The wine we really drink is our own blood.
Our bodies ferment in these barrels.
We give everything for a glass of this.
We give our minds for a sip."

Here Rumi talks about the divine love being a part of self and the degradation of self in boundaries or under restrictions of human limitations. Or the second line can also be interpreted as the development of souls in our bodies. In the last two lines he writes about the sacrifices one has to go through just to have a brief moment of ecstasy.

In another poem, he uses reed to symbolise the human soul longing for unity with the divine, separated from its source like a reed cut from the reedbed.

"Listen to the story told by the reed, of being separated.
Since I was cut from the reedbed, I have made this crying sound."

"Anyone apart from someone he loves
understands what I say."

This is a line from the same poem in which he implies that separation from his loved one- the divine can be understood by anyone experiencing separation through any form of love.

In a poem using the metaphor of a frog and a snake-

"When a frog slips into the water, the snake cannot get it."

This metaphor illustrates moments of safety, where the soul, like the frog, finds temporary refuge from worldly challenges i.e. represented by the snake. Water here symbolises the divine truth.

"Then the frog climbs back out and croaks, and the snake moves toward him again."

Here he talks about how frog can't always stay inside water and has to come out in the same way a person has to come back into the material world after experiencing the moment of safety with the divine. The snake or worldly challenges, temptations and responsibilities moving towards the person symbolise the unescapable and cyclical nature of this type of union.

"Even if the frog learned to hiss, still the snake would hear through the hiss the information he needed, the frog voice underneath."

"But if the frog could be completely silent, then the snake would go back to sleeping, and the frog could reach the barley."

The soul lives there in the silent breath."

Rumi talks about the situation where if a person learns to pretend to adapt to the material world, the worldly temptations would catch the pretence and extract the needed from the person. However, if the person engages in an introspective, personal and silent practice, then the worldly affairs would go away from disturbing and that will become that aid towards the path to reach the divine and inner peace.

The image of a candle's flame to represent the soul's journey toward spiritual enlightenment.

"A candle is made to become entirely flame.

In that annihilating moment it has no shadow.

It is nothing but a tongue of light describing a refuge."

Here, the candle's transformation into flame symbolizes the soul's quest for enlightenment, leaving the darkness of worldly concerns. The flame represents a spiritual entity, free from the burdens of ego and material attachments.

"Look at this just-finishing candle stub as someone who is finally safe from virtue and vice, the pride and the shame we claim from those."

Rumi's reflection on the transient nature of worldly virtues, suggesting that true safety lies in surpassing these dualities is depicted here.

Analysis of Mystical Imagery and Symbolism

Schimmel studied Rumi's ability to find symbols in nature like orchids, birds and flowers. He uses these symbols to represent the lover and the beloved. He also uses symbols to talk about the soul's longing for reunion with the divine. Rose and nightingale; and duck finding refuge in the sea are some of the symbols used for it. He also pays attention to the smallest of the details present in nature like the analogy of a drop of water merging with the ocean under the theme of unity and oneness. Schimmel also talks about the similarity between the intoxication of ecstasy and that of wine. He connects Rumi's frequent use of the flute as a symbol to its significance in ancient Babylonian cultural symbolism.

4.2 Love and Devotion in Rumi's Poetry

Historically, in Sufi tradition, scholars and poets have struggled to define love, recognizing its profound and indescribable nature. Figures like 'Ayn-ul-quzât-e Hamedânî and Jâhiz struggled with comprehending the depth of love, suggesting it is an experience that transcends mere words. Jâhiz introduced the term "muhabbat," to highlight the connection between God and His servant. Rumi's contributions to the understanding of love is particularly evident in his works like Mathnavi and Dîvân-e Shams. Recognizing the limitations of language in defining love, Rumi compares it to a donkey stuck in mud, explaining the difficulty of capturing such a profound experience in words. In Rumi's verses, love and devotion are depicted through imagery and metaphors. He urges readers to move beyond intellectual investigation and instead look into the face of a soul consumed by love.

The lines,

"But listen to me for one moment, quit being sad. Hear blessings dropping their blossoms around you." He introduces the theme of gratitude in sadness and despair here. The time when this reminder can turn out to be a lifesaver till date.

The qazal form plays a significant role in the expression of love. Qazals have two distinct categories romantic and mystical. Romantic sonnets portray the beloved in a worldly context, accessible despite physical distance, while mystical sonnets portray a higher realm where the beloved possesses infinite knowledge and power. But, the transition between romantic and mystical sonnets lies in the interpretation rather than language itself because the language stays symbolic and rhetorical. Nezahat Başçı's comparative study of Rumi and Shakespeare explores the transformative nature of love. Rumi's qazals, especially those about the mystical dimensions, depict love as a symbol of God's Great Beauty. This approach aligns with Shakespeare's exploration of love as a factor in character development. Başçı's insights highlight the relationship between love and mysticism in Rumi's poetry. The parallels drawn between earthly and divine love highlight the universality of love's language.

4.3 Concept of Unity and Oneness

Rumi explores the concept of Wahdat al-Wujud, or the "Unity of Being." This theme is commonly seen in his work where he talks about a space where the boundaries between the soul and God dissolve, resulting in the divine union. In Rumi's view, oneness isn't just about unity with God but it is the interconnectedness of all existence. He talks about the divine present in every aspect of the universe, from the smallest atom to the grandest cosmos in his work.

Lines like,

"I searched for God and found only myself. I searched for myself and found only God." Talk about the oneness and absolute unity of self and God.

"How does a part of the world leave the world? How can wetness leave water?" These lines highlight the inseparability and interconnectedness in the concept of unity. Scholars like Annemarie Schimmel and William C. Chittick also explore Rumi's depiction of the inseparability of the individual soul from the divine.

4.4 Influence of Sufi Philosophy

Influence of Sufi Philosophy like the concept of "fana," or annihilation in God is explored by Rumi. In his poem "I am with you always," he talks about the deep bond between the lover and the beloved. In another poem, "Where Are We?", Rumi depicts the nature of the body as a faint reflection of divine love. He emphasizes personal transformation in his poem "But don't be satisfied with stories," in which he encourages seekers to follow the path towards the divine, symbolized by references to Rumi's spiritual teacher, Shams. Through his poetry, Rumi depicts of Sufi philosophical concepts using metaphors, allegories, and rhetorical questions.

Chapter 5 Kabir's Synthesis of Bhakti and Sufi Wisdom

5.1 Introduction

Kabir blended Mohammedan mysticism with the already existing theology of Brahmanism. This was the time heavily influenced by Persian mystics like Attar, Sadi, Rumi, and Hafiz. The primary factor that still makes Kabir a unique literary and religious or spiritual figure is that he simultaneously embraced Hindu and Muslim belief systems and created something beautiful and revolutionary out of it. He identified himself at once the child of Allah and Ram and so people who were fighting over religion.

Bhakti and Sufi Fusion

Kabir blends Bhakti and Sufi elements in his poetry influenced by Persian mystics. But, he wrote in local dialects making his work widely accessible and not merely for the royal or priest class placed higher in the Indian class hierarchy.

5.2 Unity and Oneness in Kabir's Verses

Kabir's verses depict the inseparable nature of the lover and the beloved. Despite of appearing separate they are united and one. He also talks about the existence of the divine not only in the beloved but in every being as in this verse by him-

“The creature is in Brahma, and Brahma is in the creature they are ever distinct, yet ever united. He Himself is the tree, the seed, and the germ. He Himself is the flower, the fruit, and the shade.”

1. "Mo Ko Kahan Dhunro Bande" (Verse 1.13)

Kabir asserts the omnipresence of God, stating that God is not confined to temples, mosques, or any place of worship. A true lover will find the beloved everywhere and in everything.

“O servant, where dost thou seek Me? Lo! I am beside thee. I am neither in temple nor in mosque I am neither in Kaaba nor in Kailash. If thou art a true seeker, thou shalt at once see Me thou shalt meet Me in a moment of time. Kabir says, "O Sadhu! God is the breath of all breath."

2. "Santan Jat Na Pucho Nirguniyan" (Verse 1.16)

Kabir dismisses the significance of inquiring about the caste or background of a saint. He challenges the conventional divisions based on caste and the caste system prevalent in Indian subcontinent by asserting that saints, regardless of their social background, seek the same divine truth. He highlights the futility of distinguishing between individuals based on caste, emphasizing the shared pursuit of spiritual enlightenment.

“It is needless to ask of a saint the caste to which he belongs; For the priest, the warrior, the tradesman, and all the thirty-six castes, alike are seeking for God. It is but folly to ask what the caste of a saint may be; The barber has sought God, the washerwoman, and the carpenter - Even Raidas was a seeker after God. The Rishi Swapacha was a tanner by caste. Hindus and Moslems alike have achieved that End, where remains no mark of distinction.”

5.3 Influence of Sufi Philosophy in Kabir's Verses

1. "Dariya Ki Lahar Dariyaav Hai Ji" (Verse XIV.56)

Kabir employs the metaphor of the river and its waves to convey the interconnectedness of existence. The continuous flow of the river represents the eternal nature of life, and the waves, though distinct, are inherently part of the same. This imagery reflects Sufi teachings on the oneness of all creation and the connection between the seeker and the divine.

"Dariya ki lahar dariyaav hai ji, Dariyaav aur lahar men bhinn koyam. Uthe to neer hai bhaithe to neer hai, Kaho jo doosraa kis tarah hoyam. Usee ka pher ke naam lahar dharaa, Lahar ke kahe kyad neer khoyam. Jakt hee pher jab jakt parbrahm men, Gyaan kar dekh maal goyam."

2. "Angadhiya Deva" (Verse XIII.37)

Kabir, in this verse, critiques the diversity in worship practices and the multiplicity of divine forms particularly in Hinduism. He challenges the conventional understanding of God's worship, highlighting the formless nature of the Supreme. By questioning rituals and external observances, Kabir aligns with Sufi ideals that prioritize a direct and experiential connection with the divine.

"O Lord Increate, who will serve Thee? Every votary offers his worship to the God of his own creation each day he receives service. None seek Him, the Perfect Brahma, the Indivisible Lord. They believe in ten Avatars; but no Avatar can be the lock upon the Infinite Spirit, for he suffers the results of his deeds. The Supreme One must be other than this."

3. Kabir's Personal Revelation (Verse 3)

Kabir shares a personal insight, declaring that the beloved Lord is within. This revelation aligns with the Sufi concept of the divine residing within the heart of the seeker.

Kabir says

"Listen to me, my friend! My beloved Lord is within."

5.4 Mystical Imagery and Symbolism in Kabir's Verses

1. "Hamsa, Kaho Puratan Bat" (Verse XII.24)

In this verse, Kabir addresses the mythical swan, Hamsa. The swan, often symbolic of purity and transcendence, is a metaphor for the lover's quest for the divine.

"Tell me, O Swan, your ancient tale. From what land do you come, O Swan? to what shore will you fly? Where would you take your rest, O Swan, and what do you seek? Even this morning, O Swan, awake, arise, follow me! There is a land where no doubt nor sorrow have rule where the terror of Death is no more."

2. "Chandaa Jhalkai Yahi Ghat Mahin" (Verse VI.83)

Kabir uses celestial imagery in this verse i.e. the moon, sun, and the unstruck drum of eternity symbolize the divine present within, beyond the perception of ordinary senses. Or it can also mean that ignorance or lack of knowledge results in the neglect of what is always and has been always present within. Then he talks about the concept of ego i.e. I and possession i.e. Mine and how the attachment to the two is a hinderance in the spiritual journey. He ends it by saying that when one lets go of these then the divine is achievable or achieved and then one is blessed with the grace of the supreme.

"The moon shines in my body, but my blind eyes cannot see it The moon is within me, and so is the sun. The unstruck drum of eternity is sounded within me; but my deaf ears cannot hear it. So long as man clamours for the I and the Mine, his works are as naught When all love of the I and the Mine is dead, then the work of the Lord is done."

3. "Is Ghat Antar Bag Bagiche" (Verse VIII.101)

Kabir employs the metaphor of an earthen vessel to depict the vastness of creation within the individual. This vessel contains symbolic elements such as oceans, stars, and the creator, highlighting the

omnipresence of the divine within the finite human form. The imagery depicts the interconnectedness of the microcosm and macrocosm.

“Within this earthen vessel are bowers and groves, and within it is the Creator Within this vessel are the seven oceans and the unnumbered stars. The touchstone and the jewel-appraiser are within; And within this vessel the Eternal soundest, and the spring wells up.”

5.5 Love in Kabir's Verses

1. "Tohi Mori Lagan Lagaye Re Phakir Wa" (Verse I.121)

In this verse, Kabir addresses the divine with deep affection, portraying himself as a devotee, a Fakir, whose love for the Supreme is firm. The metaphor of being awakened from slumber in the personal chamber symbolizes the soul's awakening to divine consciousness. Kabir describes being rescued from the ocean of worldly attachments.

“To Thee Thou hast drawn my love, O Fakir! I was sleeping in my own chamber, and Thou didst awaken me; striking me with Thy voice, O Fakir! I was drowning in the deeps of the ocean of this world, and Thou didst save me upholding me with Thine arm, O Fakir! Only one word and no second - and Thou hast made me tear off all my bonds, O Fakir! Kabir says, "Thou hast united Thy heart to my heart, O Fakir!"

2. "I Played Day and Night with My Comrades"

Kabir uses the metaphor of playing with comrades to illustrate the human experience. The fear and awe associated with approaching the divine are depicted through the imagery of a high palace. The veil symbolizes the barriers between the lover and the Beloved.

“I played day and night with my comrades, and now I am greatly afraid. So high is my Lord's palace, my heart trembles to mount its stairs yet I must not be shy, if I would enjoy His love. My heart must cleave to my Lover; I must withdraw my veil and meet Him with all my body Mine eyes must perform the ceremony of the lamps of love. Kabir says "Listen to me, friend he understands who loves. If you feel not love's longing for your Beloved One, it is vain to adorn your body, vain to put unguent on your eyelids.”

Chapter 6 Cross-Cultural Connections

6.1 Shared Sufi Themes in Rumi and Kabir

Rumi and Kabir, though separated by geography and time, both delve into spiritual themes in their poetry, showcasing the universal essence of Sufism and Bhakti across different cultures and periods. Rumi, deeply influenced by Persian Sufism, and Kabir, rooted in medieval India's spiritual traditions, both highlight the transformative power of love and the direct connection between individuals and the Divine. Rumi, born in 1207 in Persia (now Afghanistan), steeped in Sufism's mystical tradition, emphasizes the soul's journey towards unity with God. In his poetry, Rumi often praises divine love as the ultimate path to spiritual enlightenment, portraying it as a force that transcends worldly attachments and leads seekers to ecstatic union with the Beloved. Characterized by passionate longing and mystical imagery, Rumi's verses resonate with readers from various backgrounds, inspiring them to seek inner truth and transformation. Conversely, Kabir, a mystic poet from 15th-century India, embodies the spirit of the Bhakti movement in his poetry. This movement arose in response to medieval India's rigid caste system and religious orthodoxy. Kabir's verses are infused with devotion (bhakti) and a profound love for God. Like Rumi, Kabir stresses the importance of forging a direct, personal connection with the Divine, transcending religious rituals and dogma. In their simple and direct verses, Rumi and Kabir convey deep spiritual truths and universal teachings that resonate with people from all backgrounds. Despite their different cultural upbringings, they share common themes in their poetry, like seeking spiritual unity, the power of love, and rejecting religious formalities for direct spiritual experience. Both poets challenge traditional views of religious authority and stress the importance of the soul's inner journey. Moreover, Rumi and Kabir's poetry goes beyond religious and cultural boundaries, addressing the universal human desire for spiritual fulfillment. While Rumi is influenced by Islamic mysticism and Persian Sufism, Kabir's poetry reflects the blended nature of Indian spirituality, mixing Hinduism, Islam, and Sufism. Despite these varied influences,

both poets convey a message of love, unity, and spiritual awakening that transcends any specific religious tradition. Rumi and Kabir's poetry shares profound Sufi themes that continue to inspire truth-seekers across generations and cultures. Through their timeless verses, they encourage readers to explore themselves and grow spiritually, reminding us of humanity's universal pursuit of inner peace and divine love.

Concept of Oneness

Rumi and Kabir talk about unity in their poems. They show how the self and the divine, and the individual and the universe, come together as one. Rumi talks a lot about the lover and the beloved joining, which represents the soul connecting with the divine. This connection is the highest point of a spiritual journey, where everything blends in divine love. Rumi's poems, full of longing and surrender, go beyond the ego and reveal how everything is connected. Similarly, Kabir's poetry explores the unity between humans and the divine. He says that everyone has a piece of the divine inside them, connecting them to the bigger picture. Kabir often uses examples like the ocean and the drop to explain this connection, showing how each person is a part of something greater. Through his poems, Kabir shows how the divine is everywhere, bringing unity and a sense of belonging. Both Rumi and Kabir agree that everything in the universe is linked to the divine source. Rumi and Kabir's poetry celebrate unity, transcending language, culture, and religion. They remind us that we're not separate from the universe but essential parts of a bigger picture. Moreover, their idea of oneness extends to all creation. They talk about a harmonious relationship between humans, nature, and the divine, showing how everything is interconnected. In their poems, the natural world reflects the divine, urging readers to see the sacredness in every living thing and the interconnectedness that supports us all. Rumi and Kabir's poetry deeply understand oneness, where all boundaries fade in the realization of our interconnected existence. Through their verses, they encourage readers to move past the illusion of separateness and embrace the unity of all beings. Their message of unity, love, and harmony continues to inspire truth-seekers worldwide, across generations and cultures.

Accessible Vernacular Expression

Rumi and Kabir had a gift for expressing deep spiritual truths in everyday language, making their poetry accessible to a wide audience. Despite dealing with complex ideas, both poets used words that anyone could understand. Rumi, known for works like the Mathnavi, often told stories to teach spiritual lessons. Through allegories and anecdotes, he shared insights about love, faith, and life's challenges. By grounding his ideas in relatable tales, Rumi helped people grasp the deeper meanings behind his words. Whether depicting the journey of love or the quest for spiritual union, Rumi's use of simple language and vivid imagery captivated listeners and readers alike. Similarly, Kabir's poetry drew on ordinary life experiences, using everyday activities, nature, and emotions to convey his spiritual wisdom. Kabir often infused his verses with humor and wit, reflecting his straightforward style. By using familiar language and imagery, Kabir made his poetry accessible to everyone, from laborers to scholars. Rumi and Kabir had a unique talent for touching the hearts of their audience, making them reflect on life's ordinary moments. Their use of simple language connected people from different backgrounds to universal themes like love and unity. Their poetry went beyond language and cultural barriers, speaking to the shared human experience. Whether discussing daily joys or divine mysteries, Rumi and Kabir spoke in a way that everyone could understand. Their ability to convey deep truths in accessible language shows their skill as poets and spiritual guides. Through their poetry, they encouraged people to explore themselves and grow spiritually, inspiring generations to seek truth, love, and unity. Their words still resonate worldwide, reminding us of the power of simplicity and the common cord of humanity.

Cultural Contexts and Influences

Rumi's Persian Background

Rumi moved to Konya after spending his early years in Balk. This exposed him to various cultures influencing his work. He was raised in an Islamic family with a strong scholarly tradition and influence. He was inspired by his father's theological prominence and Persian poets like Attar and Sanai as well. The teachings of prominent figures like Ibn Arabi and Shams Tabriz shaped him. So, his cultural background and poetic style were highly influenced by the blending of Islamic mysticism with Persian literature.

Kabir's Indian Heritage

Kabir was born in Varanasi during medieval India. He was in a cultural environment that combined Hindu and Sufi traditions. His contact with the Bhakti movement and the philosophy of Sant Mat greatly inspired him. The Bhakti tradition, which focused on direct communion with the divine, formed his passionate poetry. Additionally, his interactions with Hindu and Muslim saints, along with his use of rural Indian imagery, reflected the diverse cultural influences that shaped him.

Cross-Cultural Dynamics

Despite their geographical and cultural differences, Rumi and Kabir both engaged with cross-cultural influences in their work. Rumi's blend of Persian, Central Asian, and Islamic traditions resembled Kabir's fusion of Hindu, Muslim, and indigenous Indian spiritual cultures in artistic expression in their poetry.

Impact of Sufism on the Broader Cultural Milieu

Sufism's Cultural Influence

Sufism not only influenced the poets but also the wider culture of their regions. For Rumi, Sufism's impact can be seen in the vibrant cultural scene of the Islamic world during the medieval era. Sufi orders, known for their focus on inner spirituality, poetry, and music, left a lasting impression on the arts, society, and intellect of the time.

Kabir's Influence on Indian Culture

Kabir, deeply rooted in both the Bhakti and Sufi traditions, significantly shaped the culture of medieval India. His poems with Sufi ideas of love, unity, and devotion, still act as a cultural link between Hindu and Muslim communities.

Cultural Exchange and Dialogue

Sufism encourages inclusivity, fostering a culture of dialogue and exchange. Rumi's impact on Persian literature and Islamic mysticism, as well as Kabir's influence on the Bhakti movement, highlight the cultural impacts of Sufism.

6.2 Syncretism and Variation in Sufi Poetry

Variation in Expression

Rumi and Kabir were poets who shared spiritual ideas through their poetry. But they had different styles because of where they came from. Rumi was from Persia, which is now Afghanistan. He grew up with Sufi teachings and wrote poems like the Mathnavi and Divan-e Shams-e Tabrizi. Rumi's poetry talks a lot about love and how it helps to connect with God. Kabir, on the other hand, lived in North India during the 15th century. He wrote poems like the Bijak and Kabir Granthavali. Kabir's poetry was influenced by both

Hinduism and Islam, and he wanted to bring people from different religions together through his poems. His poetry is simple and easy to understand, and it talks about love and devotion to God. Even though Rumi and Kabir wrote differently, they both believed in the importance of love, unity, and changing ourselves for the better. Kabir's poetry is down-to-earth and reflects Indian spirituality, while Rumi's poems are more elegant and show the beauty of Persian mysticism. Together, Rumi and Kabir's poems tell stories that make us think about life and God. Their poetry is still important today because it helps people find peace and meaning in their lives, no matter where they come from or what they believe. In summary, Rumi and Kabir were poets who used simple words to talk about big ideas like love and God. Even though they came from different places and wrote in different styles, their poetry continues to inspire people to be better and find happiness in their spiritual journey.

Chapter 7 Conclusion

7.1 Summary of Findings

In this analysis, of Rumi and Kabir's poetry, a number of themes about their spiritual teachings and legacy have been discussed. The themes of love and spirituality reflect their deep stances on the transformative power of divine love in union and oneness of all beings. The beautiful idea of Wahdat al-Wujud literally means the unity of being and Fana denotes the destruction of self in pursuit of God. In depth study of the spiritual poets has been made possible by words of some of the major literary scholars. Annemarie Schimmel and William C. Chittick contributed significantly to understand the philosophical nature and spiritual depth of Rumi's poetry. Their contributions help in a better understanding of the poets teachings and wisdom by elucidating the complex levels of meaning and symbolism constructed within the words he wrote. Additionally, the comparative analysis of Sufi elements in their poetry revealed that despite being from different cultural backgrounds, there are striking similarities between the themes used by them in their writings. Both wrote about love, unity and spiritual enlightenment beyond the cultural, linguistic, religious, and geographical barriers. Their poetry is about the universal human desire for inner peace and spiritual satisfaction. So, the examination of Sufi elements in their poetry highlight the themes of eternal knowledge and profound spiritual revelations in their lyrics. The purpose of their writings was to motivate others to walk the path of righteousness, self-discovery and inner growth. Transcending linguistic, geographical and cultural barriers their poetry resonates with truth seekers around the globe. May their eternal words provide comfort, wisdom, and enlightenment to readers and seekers alike as we keep exploring their poetry.

7.2 Implications for Cross-Cultural Understanding

This study of cross-cultural connections emphasizes the shared human quest for the divine across geographical and cultural boundaries. This highlights the potential for cross-cultural understanding through the universal language of mysticism.

7.3 Recommendations for Further Research

Comparative analyses with other mystical traditions or religions like Sikhism, detailed investigations into the socio-religious influences on Sufi poets or the connection of Islam with it, and the contemporary relevance of Sufi themes in the global spiritual discourse could offer more insights. In conclusion, the findings aim to contribute to a better understanding of Sufi philosophy, emphasizing its potential for cross-cultural understanding.

References

1. Rūmī, Jalāl al-Dīn (Maulana), *The Essential Rumi*, 1999.
2. Kabir, *One Hundred Poems*, DigiCat, 29 May 2022.
3. Schimmel, Annemarie, *Mystical Dimensions of Islam*, University of North Carolina Press, 8 Aug. 2011.
4. Chittick, William C., *The Sufi Path of Love*, State University of New York Press, 30 June 1984.
5. Lewis, Franklin D., *Rumi - Past and Present, East and West*, Simon and Schuster, 1 Oct. 2014.
6. Citlak, Faith, *Rumi and His Sufi Path of Love*, Tughra Books, 1 May 2007.
7. Kabir, et al., *The Bījāk of Kabir*, Delhi, Motilal Banarsidass Publishers Private Limited, 2015.
8. Sinha, Chandan, *VISION of WISDOMSELECTED SAKHIS*, Rupa Publications India Pvt Limited, 1 Nov. 2020.
9. Schomer, Karine, *The Sants Studies in a Devotional Tradition of India*, Delhi U.A., Motilal Banarsidass, 1987.
10. Bly, Robert, *Kabir*, Beacon Press, 1 Aug. 2011.
11. Jlmeyer1, Post author, "Poetry of Rumi," *Global and Historical Studies China and the Islamic Middle East Reader*, blogs.butler.edu/ghs208reader/2019/12/19/poetry-of-rumi-ghs-reader-pg-227-236/. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
12. Contributors, et al., "The Reed Flute's Song," *The On Being Project*, 9 Oct. 2020, onbeing.org/poetry/song-of-the-reed/.
13. "A Quote from the Essential Rumi," *Goodreads*, Goodreads, www.goodreads.com/quotes/9073518-when-a-frog-slips-into-the-water-the-snake-cannot. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
14. *Universalspirituality.blog*, "Enough Words – Rumi," *Universal Spirituality*, 21 Oct. 2019, universalspirituality.blog/2017/11/10/enough-words-rumi/.
15. Radhikab, "Rumi Poem Interpretation- Enough Words," *Read between the Lines*, 15 Feb. 2022, readbetweenthelines111.com/2017/09/14/first-blog-post/.
16. Noble, Barnes &, "A Year with Rumi Daily Readings|Hardcover," Barnes & Noble, www.barnesandnoble.com/w/a-year-with-rumi-coleman-barks/1137180645. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
17. "Burnt Kabob - Quest for Meaning," *Www.questformeaning.org*, www.questformeaning.org/spiritual-themes/burnt-kabob-rumi/. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
18. "Rabindranath Tagore - Verses - One Hundred Poems of Kabir - 7 (When He Himself Reveals)," *Www.tagoreweb.in*, www.tagoreweb.in/Verses/one-hundred-poems-of-kabir-202/when-he-himself-reveals-3860. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
19. Affairs, Berkley Center for Religion, Peace and World, "Kabir Songs of Kabir on the Nature of God (C. 1440-1518)," berkleycenter.georgetown.edu/quotes/kabir-songs-of-kabir-on-the-nature-of-god-c-1440-1518/. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
20. Poet Seers, "O Servant Where Dost Thou Seek Me?," *Www.poetseers.org*, www.poetseers.org/the-poetseers/kabir/kabir-index/o-servant-where-dost-thou-seek-me/. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
21. Saint, "It Is Needless to Ask of a Saint by Kabir," *Allpoetry.com*, allpoetry.com/poem/14326997-It-Is-Needless-To-Ask-Of-A-Saint-by-Kabir. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
22. "Poem It Is Needless to Ask of a Saint by Kabir," *Www.poetrynook.com*, www.poetrynook.com/poem/it-needless-ask-saint. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
23. "One Hundred Poems of Kabir/XIV - Wikisource, the Free Online Library," *En.wikisource.org*, en.wikisource.org/wiki/One_Hundred_Poems_of_Kabir/XIV. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
24. "One Hundred Poems of Kabir/XIV - Wikisource, the Free Online Library," *En.wikisource.org*, en.m.wikisource.org/wiki/One_Hundred_Poems_of_Kabir/XIV. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
25. huzaifazoom, "Tagore/Kabir XIII. X," *Gathering Just-a-Bit-o Moss*, 21 Aug. 2016, huzaifazoom.wordpress.com/2016/08/21/tagorekabir-xiii-x/. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.
26. "The Songs of Kabir XIII," *Sacred-Texts.com*, sacred-texts.com/hin/sok/sok014.htm. Accessed 31 Mar. 2024.